

Explanation of the Gibbs paradox

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Abstract

The Gibbs paradox is one of the most mysterious physical paradoxes. It arises when considering fairly simple questions concerning the entropy of a mixture or the entropy of the mixing of ideal gases, but for more than a hundred years there has not been a generally accepted explanation.

This article shows that the reasoning by which the Gibbs paradox occurs contains an error. The entropy of a mixture of ideal gases is found by summation of the entropy of these gases, which implies the additivity of entropy. The entropy of ideal gases is expressed by the formula that contains the term $Rn \ln(V/n)$ (n is a number of moles of gas, V is a volume of gas, R is ideal gas constant) or equivalent formulas. The function expressed by the formula of this form is not an additive function in the case when different or identical ideal gases form a mixture. Therefore, a quantity called the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases is a function of a different form than the entropy of pure ideal gas: this formula contains a term, which is not present in a formula of the entropy of pure ideal gas.

However, the sum of the entropies of different ideal gases that form a mixture and the entropy of pure ideal gas are mistakenly considered as functions of the same form. As a result, in the reasoning in which the values of these functions are compared, inexplicable conclusions appear, known as various formulations of the Gibbs paradox.

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1. Introduction

The Gibbs paradox is one of the most mysterious physical paradoxes. It has been known for over a hundred years. It was explained or discussed by J.W. Gibbs, M. Planck, J.D. van der Waals, H.A. Lorentz, A. Sommerfeld, E. Schrödinger and other well-known physicists (see [1–9]). The solutions to this paradox are presented in many textbooks (see, e.g., [2–6,10–15]), but papers containing new explanations appear again and again (see, e.g., [16–21] and ArXiv (arxiv.org)). This is despite the fact that the paradox arises when considering the simplest systems studied in thermodynamics — ideal gases and their mixtures.

There are several formulations (versions, kinds) of the Gibbs paradox. In one of them we are talking about the entropy of mixing of ideal gases during the transition from mixing different to mixing identical gases (see, e.g., [1,2,7,13,16,18–27]). Suppose that two different, chemically non-interacting ideal gases with equal temperature and pressure are separated by an impenetrable partition. After the partition is removed, the gases mix, and the entropy of the system increases by the value of entropy of mixing, which, according to the calculation, does not depend on the nature and degree of difference of gases. If identical gases with the same temperature and pressure mix, then the entropy of mixing is zero. Thus, if it is assumed that the properties of gases approach each other, then the entropy of mixing remains constant, when there is some, even infinitely small, difference between the gases. When the gases become identical, the entropy of mixing jumps to zero. This behaviour of the entropy of mixing is paradoxical.

Another formulation of this paradox concerns a similar behaviour of the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases: in going from a mixture of different gases to a mixture of identical gases by converging property values of gases, the value of the entropy of the system undergoes a jump (discontinuity) during the transition from infinitely little different property values to the same values (see, e.g., [28,29]).

There are also other formulations of the Gibbs paradox (see, e.g., [3–6,9–12,14–21,25–28,30]), which will be discussed below.

Earlier, the author drew attention to two features of this paradox, which were not taken into account by anyone.

Firstly, paradoxical conclusions are made not on the basis of processing empirical data, but in the course of reasoning based on certain premises. It follows that by analysing this reasoning, one can establish the premises from which paradoxical conclusions follow and significantly narrow thereby the range of search for the solution of the problem.

Secondly, a number of formulations of the Gibbs paradox, including the above two, concern the peculiarities of the mathematical behaviour of quantities which are functions of many variables, and these functions can be expressed by formulas. It follows that the premises from which conclusions about the paradoxical behaviour of these quantities follow can be established quite accurately. The functions that are expressed by formulas cannot have the peculiarities of behaviours which are not associated with the form of formulas and the peculiarities of change in the arguments or parameters of these formulas.

Having taken into account these peculiarities of the Gibbs paradox, the author has analysed corresponding reasonings and established the premises from which conclusions about paradoxical jumps in mixture entropy and mixing entropy of ideal gases follow. Among these premises are the following: “The formulas for the entropy of a pure ideal gas contains a terms of the form $Rn \ln n$ ”, where n is the number of moles of the gas, R is a constant, and “The mixture entropy of ideal gases is equal to the sum of the entropies of the [mixture] components” (see [31,32]).

After some time, the author came to the conclusion that the two above premises are logically incompatible [31,33] (cannot be true at the same time), which gives rise to paradoxical conclusions. However, he did not give a convincing rationale for this conclusion. Recently, the author realized that it is possible to convincingly prove the logical incompatibility (inconsistency) of these premises and to explain the Gibbs paradox, if we take into account the properties of additive quantities and additive functions. This is shown briefly in Ref. [34] and in greater detail below.

2. On additive quantities, properties, functions

The quantity has the property of additivity and is called additive if its value A , corresponding to a whole object, is equal to the sum of its values A_i , which correspond to the parts of the object under any partition of the object into parts (see, e.g., [35,36]):

$$A = \sum A_i . \tag{2.1}$$

Examples of additive quantities are the length of a line, surface area, the volume of a solid.

Additive quantities and additive properties of substances are mass m , the number of moles n , the number of particles N , weight P , heat capacity C , and a number of other properties of pure (homogeneous) substances. For some amount of a pure (homogeneous) substance, relations that are particular cases of formula (2.1) hold:

$$m = m_1 + m_2, \quad (2.2)$$

$$n = n_1 + n_2, \quad (2.3)$$

$$N = N_1 + N_2, \quad (2.4)$$

$$C = C_1 + C_2. \quad (2.5)$$

In these formulas, the letters without indices denote the values of corresponding quantities for some amount of a pure substance, and the letters with indices denote the values of corresponding quantities for parts 1 and 2 of this amount of the same substance.

The same relations are valid for ideal mixtures of substances. If it is assumed that the letters without indices in formulas (2.2)—(2.5) denote the values of the corresponding properties of binary ideal mixtures of substances, and that the letters with indices denote the values of the properties of the components of these mixtures, then these formulas will express relations between the properties of ideal mixtures and their components.

The functions obeying the Cauchy functional equation (see [37,38]) of the form:

$$f(y_1 + y_2) = f(y_1) + f(y_2) \quad (2.6)$$

are called additive functions.

If y_1 and y_2 are real numbers, and $f(y)$ is a continuous function, then the solution of the functional equation (2.6) is a homogeneous linear function of the form:

$$f(y) = by. \quad (2.7)$$

For the proof of this statement see [Ibid].

It is easy to verify that every additive property of substances, including those listed above, is an additive function of any other additive property of substances: all of them are related to one another by relations of the forms (2.6) and (2.7). Specifically, for any additive property of some amount of the i -th substance, the relation:

$$A_i = a_i n_i, \quad (2.8)$$

holds, where a_i is the mole value of the additive property A for the i -th substance:

$$a_i = \frac{A_i}{n_i}. \quad (2.9)$$

It follows from (2.1), (2.3), (2.8) for a binary ideal mixture that

$$A_m = a_1 n_1 + a_2 n_2 = a_m (n_1 + n_2) = a_m n, \quad (2.10)$$

where A_m is the value of the additive property A for a binary ideal mixture, a_m is the average mole value of the additive property A for the mixture:

$$a_m = \frac{A_m}{n} = \frac{A_1 + A_2}{n_1 + n_2} = \frac{a_1 n_1 + a_2 n_2}{n_1 + n_2}. \quad (2.11)$$

$$a_m = a_1 x_1 + a_2 x_2, \quad (2.12)$$

where x_i (x_1 and x_2) is the mole fractions of the substances in the mixture:

$$x_i = \frac{n_i}{n} = \frac{n_i}{n_1 + n_2}. \quad (2.13)$$

It should be added that a particular case of formula (2.11) is the formula for average molar heat capacity at the constant volume of a binary mixture of ideal gases, c_{vm} :

$$c_{vm} = \frac{n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}}{n_1 + n_2} = \frac{n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}}{n}, \quad (2.14)$$

where c_{v1} and c_{v2} are molar heat capacities at the constant volume of gases 1 and 2.

The formulas of the forms (2.10)—(2.12), which relate the additive properties of binary ideal mixtures to the specific properties, masses and mass fractions of the components, can be obtained by the same derivation based on formulas (2.1) and (2.2). They are given in many books, in the sections devoted to mixtures (see, e.g., [15,35]).

3. On the additivity of the entropy of an ideal gas

The additivity of the mass, weight, heat capacity and a number of other properties of substances is established and can be empirically tested — according to measurements of the values of the corresponding values for a certain amount of a substance and for parts of this amount of a substance.

The additivity of the entropy of substances cannot be verified experimentally, since entropy is a physical quantity that cannot be measured directly. However, entropy is a function of state, i.e. a certain function of the parameters of thermodynamic systems. If the entropy of a thermodynamic system is expressed in terms of its parameters by a known formula, then it is possible to find out whether the entropy of this system is an additive quantity or not without recourse to an experiment. Firstly, the result of calculation of the entropy of a thermodynamic system can be compared with the sum of the entropy values of the parts of this system. Secondly, since the additive properties of substances are additive functions of the amount of substances, the conclusion about the additivity of the entropy of a substance can be drawn from the form of the dependence of the entropy of this substance on its amount.

The entropy of ideal gases in thermodynamics courses and in papers dealing with the Gibbs paradox (see, e.g., [1,2,13,15,24,30]) is expressed by formulas of the forms:

$$S_i = n_i \left(c_{vi} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V_i}{n_i} + s_{0vi} \right), \quad (3.1)$$

$$S_i = N_i \left(f_i(T) + k \ln \frac{V_i}{N_i} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

$$S_i = n_i (c_{pi} \ln T - R \ln p_i + s_{0pi}), \quad (3.3)$$

$$S_i = m_i \left(c_{vi}^m \ln T + R_i \ln \frac{V_i}{m_i} + s_{0vi}^m \right), \quad (3.4)$$

where S_i is the entropy of some amount of the i -th ideal gas, T is the thermodynamic (absolute) temperature of the gas, V_i is its volume, p_i is its pressure, c_{vi} and c_{pi} are the molar heat capacities of the i -th ideal gas at a constant volume and at a constant pressure respectively, c_{vi}^m is the specific heat capacity of the i -th ideal gas at a constant volume, R is universal gas constant, k is Boltzmann constant, R_i is the specific gas constant of the i -th ideal gas, $f_i(T)$ is a certain function of temperature; s_{0vi} , s_{0pi} , s_{0vi}^m are constants.

Note that in papers dealing with the Gibbs paradox these formulas generally appear without terms which include constants of the form c_i and s_{0vi} .

Note also that the relationship of a number of parameters of the state of ideal gases can be expressed by the formula:

$$p_i V_i = n_i R T = N_i k T = m_i R_i T. \quad (3.5)$$

See, e.g., [6,13,15,24].

According to formulas (3.1), (3.2), (3.4), the entropy of an ideal gas is not a homogeneous linear function of the additive quantities n_i , N_i , m_i ; it follows that in the general case, it is not an additive function and hence is not an additive quantity. Therefore, it is not to be expected that the entropy of an ideal gas will be equal to the sum of the entropies of parts of the gas with any partition of the gas into parts.

Let us examine whether the entropy of an ideal gas is equal to the sum of the entropies of its parts when certain restrictions are imposed on the partition of the gas into parts. To this end, let us calculate and compare the entropy values of n moles of the i -th ideal gas and the sum of the entropies of its two parts (n_1 and n_2 moles) for two methods of partition of the gas into parts.

In the first method of partition, the parts of the gas are in different places in space and have equal temperature and pressure values, which are equal to those of the gas. In this case, the volume of the gas is the sum of the volumes of the parts:

$$V = V_1 + V_2. \quad (3.6)$$

In the second method, the parts are in the same place and form a mixture. In this case, the volumes of the gas and its parts are equal:

$$V = V_1 = V_2. \quad (3.7)$$

In the first and second cases, the amount of the gas in its parts is related to the total amount of the gas by relations (2.2)—(2.4).

To make it clear without additional explanation, the entropy of which gases with what parameters is considered, the entropy of a certain amount of i -th, 1st and 2nd gas is designated as a function of the quantities that unambiguously determine its value: $S_i(n, V, T)$, $S_i(n_1, V_1, T)$, $S_i(n_2, V_2, T)$, $S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)$, $S_1(n_1, V_1, T)$, $S_2(n_2, V_2, T)$, $S_1(n_1, V, T)$, $S_2(n_2, V, T)$.

For the first method of partition, it follows from (3.5), (2.3), (2.4) in view of (3.6) that

$$\frac{V_1}{n_1} = \frac{V_2}{n_2} = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{n_1 + n_2} = \frac{V}{n} = \frac{V_1}{N_1} = \frac{V_2}{N_2} = \frac{V_1 + V_2}{N_1 + N_2} = \frac{V}{N}, \quad (3.8)$$

From (3.1), (3.8), (2.3) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & S_i(n_1, V_1, T) + S_i(n_2, V_2, T) = \\ & = (n_1 + n_2)c_{vi} \ln T + n_1 R \ln \frac{V_1}{n_1} + n_2 R \ln \frac{V_2}{n_2} + (n_1 + n_2)s_{0vi} = . \\ & = n \left(c_{vi} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + s_{0vi} \right) = S_i(n, V, T) \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Formula (3.9) demonstrates that in the case where the parts of the ideal gas are in different places, and their temperatures and pressures are equal, the sum of the entropies of the parts of the gas is equal to the entropy of an ideal gas.

Now suppose that the parts of the i -th gas (n_1 and n_2 moles) form a mixture.

For this case, it follows from formulas (3.1) and (2.3) in view of (3.7) that

$$\begin{aligned} & S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T) = \\ & = (n_1 + n_2)c_{vi} \ln T + n_1 R \ln \frac{V}{n_1} + n_2 R \ln \frac{V}{n_2} + (n_1 + n_2)s_{0vi} = , \\ & = n \left(c_{vi} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + s_{0vi} \right) + L_x(n_1, n_2) \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$L_x(n_1, n_2) = R(n_1 + n_2) \ln(n_1 + n_2) - Rn_1 \ln n_1 - Rn_2 \ln n_2 = -nR(x_1 \ln x_1 + x_2 \ln x_2) = -nR[x_1 \ln x_1 + (1 - x_1) \ln(1 - x_1)] = -nR[x_2 \ln x_2 + (1 - x_2) \ln(1 - x_2)] \quad (3.11)$$

x_1 and x_2 are given by formula (2.13).

Note that if $n_1 = n_2 = 1$, then $L_x(n_1, n_2) = 2R \ln 2$, and that if $n_1 = n_2 = 0,5$, then $L_x(n_1, n_2) = R \ln 2$.

Formula (3.10) demonstrates that if the parts of the gas form a mixture (are in the same place), then the sum of the entropies of the parts of the gas is not equal to the entropy of the ideal gas, but exceeds the entropy of the ideal gas by the quantity of $L_x(n_1, n_2)$:

$$S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T) = S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T) + L_x(n_1, n_2). \quad (3.12)$$

The appearance of $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ in the formula (3.10) is due to the non-additivity of the function $Rn_i \ln(V_i / n_i)$, provided that $V_i = V$. The non-additivity of the function $Rn_i \ln(V_i / n_i)$ under this condition is due to the fact that $(n_1 + n_2) \ln(n_1 + n_2) \neq n_1 \ln n_1 + n_2 \ln n_2$.

It follows from (3.12) that functions $S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T)$ and $S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)$ are functions of different form. If $S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)$ depends only on the total amount of gas $n = n_1 + n_2$, then $S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T)$ also depends on the amount of gas in parts n_1 and n_2 .

Attention should be paid to the difference of the non-additivity of the entropy of ideal gas, provided that its parts form a mixture, from the non-additivity of the properties of substances in the case of formation of non-ideal mixtures. Deviations from additivity in non-ideal mixtures are revealed when comparing the values of properties of mixtures, obtained by measurements, with those of properties of mixtures calculated from formula (2.1) or (2.10). These deviations are attributed, within the scope of molecular theory, to the fact that in non-ideal mixtures there are interactions between molecules which are absent in ideal mixtures (e.g. long-range forces of mutual attraction or repulsion of molecules). Of course, intermolecular interactions cannot bear any relation to the non-additivity of the entropy of an ideal gas. The non-additivity of this quantity was detected not when comparing the results of measurements with the results of calculations, but in the course of calculations; it is caused by the non-additivity of the function of the entropy of ideal gas, viz. by the fact that its formula contains a term of the form $Rn_i \ln(V_i / n_i)$, which is not an additive function if the parts of the gas form a mixture and the volumes of the parts are equal to the gas volume.

Note that if the formula for the entropy of ideal gas contained not a term of the form $Rn_i \ln(V_i/n_i)$, but a term of the form $Rn_i \ln V_i$, i.e. would have the form

$$S_i = n_i (c_{vi} \ln T + R \ln V_i + s_{0vi}). \quad (3.13)$$

the sum of the entropies of the parts of some amount of ideal gas would be equal to the entropy of gas in the case where its parts form a mixture and would be lower than the entropy of gas by $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ in the case where its parts are in different places.

The same conclusions about the additivity of the entropy of ideal gas can be made on the basis of formulas (3.2)—(3.4). It also follows from formulas (3.2)—(3.4) that if the parts of gas are in different places and have equal temperature and pressure values, then the entropy of gas is equal to the sum of the entropies of its parts; if the parts of gas form a mixture, then the sum of the entropies of the parts is not equal to the entropy of gas.

The fact that the entropy of an ideal gas is equal to the sum of the entropies of its parts with one method of partition of the gas into parts and is not equal to the sum of the entropies of its parts with another method of partition of the gas into parts is not a unique feature of the entropy of ideal gas. The volume and pressure of an ideal gas have similar features. The pressure of ideal gas is equal to the sum of the pressures of its parts if they are in the same space (form a mixture) and is not equal to the sum of the pressures of the parts of gas if they are spatially separated. The volume of gas is equal to the sum of the volumes of its parts if the parts of gas are spatially separated and is not equal to the sum of the volumes of the parts of gas if they form a mixture.

4. On the sum of the entropies of different ideal gases

Suppose that there are two different ideal gases: one with the parameters n_1, c_{v1}, s_{01} and another with the parameters n_2, c_{v2}, s_{02} , and $n_1 + n_2 = n$. Using formula (3.1), let us calculate the values of the sum of the entropies of these gases for two cases. In one case, the gases are in different places (e.g. are separated by an impenetrable partition) and have equal temperature and pressure values and volumes V_1 and V_2 . In this case, relations (3.6) and (3.8) hold. In the other case, the gases form a mixture. In this case, relation (3.7) hold.

For the first case (different ideal gases are in different places), it follows from (3.1), (3.8), (2.3) in view of (3.6) that

$$\begin{aligned}
& S_1(n_1, V_1, T) + S_2(n_2, V_2, T) = \\
& = (n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}) \ln T + n_1 R \ln \frac{V_1}{n_1} + n_2 R \ln \frac{V_2}{n_2} + n_1 s_{0v1} + n_2 s_{0v2} = \\
& = n \left(\frac{n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}}{n} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + \frac{n_1 s_{0v1} + n_2 s_{0v2}}{n} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

For the second case (different ideal gases form a mixture), it follows from (3.1) and (2.3) in view of (3.7) that

$$\begin{aligned}
& S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T) = \\
& = (n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}) \ln T + n_1 R \ln \frac{V}{n_1} + n_2 R \ln \frac{V}{n_2} + n_1 s_{0v1} + n_2 s_{0v2} = , \\
& = n \left(\frac{n_1 c_{v1} + n_2 c_{v2}}{n} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + \frac{n_1 s_{0v1} + n_2 s_{0v2}}{n} \right) + L_x(n_1, n_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

where $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ is expressed by formula (3.11).

Taking into account (2.11), we determine the parameter s_{0vm} of the mixture:

$$s_{0vm} = \frac{n_1 s_{0v1} + n_2 s_{0v2}}{n} . \tag{4.3}$$

In view of (4.3) and (2.14), formula (4.2) will take the form

$$S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T) = n \left(c_{vm} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + s_{0vm} \right) + L_x(n_1, n_2) . \tag{4.4}$$

In view of (4.3) and (2.14), formula (4.1) can be written as:

$$S_1(n_1, V_1, T) + S_2(n_2, V_2, T) = n \left(c_{vm} \ln T + R \ln \frac{V}{n} + s_{0vm} \right) . \tag{4.5}$$

Formula (4.2) expresses the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture through parameters of the gases: $n_1, n_2, c_{v1}, c_{v2}, s_{0v1}, s_{0v2}, V, T$ and formula (4.4) through parameters of the mixture n, c_{vm}, s_{0vm}, V, T and through parameters of the gases n_1 and n_2 . According to (4.4), the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture is equal to the sum of two functions. The first function is of the same form as the entropy of the i -th ideal gas: it is expressed through parameters of the mixture n, c_{vm}, s_{0vm}, V, T by the same formula as the entropy of the i -th ideal gas is expressed through parameters of the gas: n, c_i, s_{0vi}, V, T . The second function is $L_x(n_1, n_2)$.

In general, the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture, which is expressed by formula (4.4), is a function of the same form as the sum of the entropies of the parts of an ideal gas that form a mixture, which is expressed by formula (3.10): formulas (4.4) and (3.10) differ only by the values of the parameters.

It should be added that the appearance of the term $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ in formulas (4.4) and (3.10) is caused by the same peculiarities of formula (3.1): by the presence of the term $n_i R \ln(V_i / n_i)$, which is independent of the molar properties of gases and is not an additive function of n_i in the case when different or identical ideal gases form a mixture. Also note that formula (3.10) is a particular case of formula (4.2): when gases 1 and 2 become identical to the i -th gas, formula (4.2) transforms into formula (3.10).

The same conclusions about the peculiarities of the sums of the entropies of different ideal gases can be made on the basis of formulas (3.2)—(3.4).

5. Why the Gibbs paradox arises

Most formulations of the Gibbs paradox is a result of reasoning in which formulas of the forms (3.1)—(3.4) are used as initial formulas, and the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases, S_m , is defined, in accordance with the Gibbs theorem (see, e.g., [2,6,13,22]), as the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture.

For a binary mixture, the Gibbs theorem is expressed by the formula:

$$S_m = S_1 + S_2. \quad (5.1)$$

Using the formulas obtained above, we show why the use of formula (5.1) and any of the formulas of the form (3.1)—(3.4) leads to the Gibbs paradox. To do this, we reproduce and analyse the reasoning in which its different formulations arise.

First of all, note that if the entropy of ideal gas is expressed by formula (3.1), and the volume of binary mixture is V , then taking into account the notations adopted above, the formula expressing the Gibbs theorem can be written as:

$$S_m = S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T). \quad (5.2)$$

It follows from formulas (5.2) and (3.1) that the entropy of a binary mixture of ideal gases is expressed by formula (4.2) or (4.4), which contain the term $L_x(n_1, n_2)$, and is a function of different form than the entropy of ideal gas, which is expressed by formula (3.1).

However, the authors who discussed the Gibbs paradox did not regard the presence of the term $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ in the formula for the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture as a ground for referring this sum to functions of another form than the entropy of ideal gas, which is expressed by formula (3.1). The fact that the term $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ is contained in formula (3.10) by virtue of the same peculiarities of formula (3.1) was not regarded by anyone as a ground for referring the sum of entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture to

functions of the same form as the sum of the entropies of the ideal-gas parts forming a mixture. The sum of the entropies of different ideal gases that form a mixture is usually attributed to functions of the same form as the entropy of an ideal gas, and called the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases. But if we assume that the mixture consists of identical gases, i.e. that is a pure gas, then formulas (4.2) and (4.4), which express this amount, not turn into the formula for the entropy of pure gas (3.1), but into the formula of another form (3.10) expressing the sum of the entropy of the gas parts forming the mixture. This gives rise to corollaries which are considered to be paradoxical. They are the subject-matter of most formulations of the Gibbs paradox.

In a number of formulations of the Gibbs paradox, the appearance of contradictions in reasoning is considered paradoxical.

Two such formulations were discussed by Ya. D. van der Waals and F. Konstamm [3]. Based on the formula for the entropy of an ideal gas, which contains a term of the form $m_i R_i \ln(V_i / m_i)$, and assuming that the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases is equal to the sum of the entropies of the mixture components, these authors had derived for the entropy of a binary mixture of ideal gases a formula containing the logarithmic term $MR\{x \log x + (1-x) \log(1-x)\}$ [Ibid]. Then in the paragraph “Gibbs Paradox” [Ibid], they noticed that this term is independent of the properties of the gases and concluded that it remains unchanged if it is assumed that the mixture consists of two identical gases. In this case, a contradiction arises: the entropy of a mixture of identical ideal gases exceeds the entropy of pure gas by the magnitude of the logarithmic term, although a mixture of identical gases is a pure gas. This conclusion, along with another, constituting a different formulation of the Gibbs paradox, they called inexplicable in the framework of thermodynamics [Ibid].

The paradox (inexplicable result) that is equivalent to this one can be formulated as follows: formula (4.2) transforms into formula (3.10), but not into (3.1), provided that $c_{v1} = c_{v2} = c_{vi}$, $s_{0v1} = s_{0v2} = s_{0vi}$. This result seems paradoxical to those who erroneously think that the formula (4.2) expresses a function of the form (3.1), and not a function of the form (3.10).

In another formulation of Gibbs paradox, contradiction arises in reasoning about the values of the entropy of mixing of two ideal gases that are initially separated by an impermeable partition.

Since entropy is a function of state, its change ΔS as a result of a change in state of thermodynamic system can be found by the formula:

$$\Delta S = S_{II} - S_I, \quad (5.3)$$

where S_I is the entropy value of the system in the initial state, and S_{II} is the entropy value of the system in the final state.

In this case, the system in its initial state is two ideal gases separated by an impenetrable partition. The entropy of such a system is found by summing the entropies of the gases (see, e.g., [2,6,13,24,30]).

If the temperature and pressure of the gases have equal values, their amounts are n_1 and n_2 , and S_i is expressed by formula (3.1), then S_I for different gases is expressed by formula (4.1) or (4.5) and for identical (i -th and i -th) gases by formula (3.10).

After removing the partition separating different gases 1 and 2, their mixture of volume V is formed. From (5.1) and (3.1) it follows that the entropy of the mixture is expressed by the formula (4.2) or (4.4). From formulas (4.1), (4.2), (5.3) (or 4.4), (4.5), (5.3) follows a formula for the mixing entropy of different ideal gases (ΔS_{md}) originally separated by a partition:

$$\Delta S_{md} = S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T) - [S_1(n_1, V_1, T) + S_2(n_2, V_2, T)] = L_x(n_1, n_2). \quad (5.4)$$

According to (5.4), the mixing entropy of different ideal gases with equal temperature and pressure values is equal to $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ and is independent of the properties of the gases being mixed. Therefore, it can be concluded that the mixing entropy of identical gases with equal temperature and pressure values, ΔS_{mi} , is also equal to $L_x(n_1, n_2)$. We can come to the same conclusion if formula (5.4) is extended to the case of mixing n_1 and n_2 moles of the i -th gas:

$$\Delta S_{mi} = S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T) - [S_i(n_1, V_1, T) + S_i(n_2, V_2, T)] = L_x(n_1, n_2). \quad (5.5)$$

But after removing the partition separating n_1 and n_2 moles of the i -th gas of volumes V_1 and V_2 with equal temperature and pressure values, $n_1 + n_2$ moles of the same i -th gas of volume V with the same temperature and pressure values are formed. With this in mind, from (3.1), (3.9), (5.3) follows this formula for ΔS_{mi} :

$$\Delta S_{mi} = S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T) - [S_i(n_1, V_1, T) + S_i(n_2, V_2, T)] = 0. \quad (5.6)$$

This result contradicts that expressed by formula (5.5). The appearance of a contradiction in obtaining the entropy of mixing of identical gases, a number of authors call the Gibbs paradox (see, e.g., [3,5–7,15]).

Comparing formulas (5.5) and (5.6), it can be noted that the contradiction (the difference in the values of formulas (5.5) and (5.6)) is due to the difference in the premises used in the calculations of the system entropy after mixing identical gases. When deriving

formula (5.5), it was assumed that when n_1 and n_2 moles of the i -th gas are mixed, a mixture of n_1 and n_2 moles of the i -th gas is formed, whose entropy is $S_i(n_1, V, T) + S_i(n_2, V, T)$, as follows from (5.1) and (3.1). When deriving (5.6), it was assumed that when n_1 and n_2 moles of the i -th gas are mixed, $n_1 + n_2$ moles of the i -th gas are formed, whose entropy is $S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)$. Since in the case where the gas is partitioned into parts, which form a mixture, its entropy is neither an additive function nor an additive quantity, the sum of the entropies of such parts is a function of a different type than the entropy of pure gas. The difference in the values of formulas (5.5) and (5.6) may be unexpected (paradoxical) only for those who mistakenly believe that the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture, which is expressed by formula (4.2) or (4.4), is a function of the same form as the entropy of an ideal gas, expressed by formula (3.1).

A number of formulations of the Gibbs paradox speak of paradoxical jumps of certain quantities.

The essence of one of these formulations (see [28 pp. 170–247]) can be stated as following. Suppose there is a mixture of two different ideal gases. The entropy of the gas is expressed by formulas of the form (3.1)—(3.4), and the entropy of the mixture is expressed by the formula (5.1). Suppose the quantities of gases do not change, and their molar (specific) properties converge. In the limit of this convergence, the gases become identical, and the mixture turns into a pure gas. As long as the gases remain different, there is nothing paradoxical in the behaviour of the entropy of the mixture: it changes in accordance with the change in the values of the molar (specific) properties of gases that are included in the formulas for entropy. But at the moment of transition from a mixture of different to a mixture of identical gases (that is, to pure gas), the entropy of the system abruptly decreases by $L_x(n_1, n_2)$. It is not clear why there is a jump in the entropy of the mixture, if it is assumed that the transition from different gases to the identical occurs without a jump. It is also not clear why the value of the jump does not depend on how and how much the mixed gases differ.

As stated above, in the case when the entropy of a pure ideal gas is expressed by the formula (3.1), the sum of the entropies of different ideal gases which form a mixture is expressed by formula (4.2) or (4.4.), and is a function of a different form than the entropy of pure gas. Formulas (4.2) and (4.4.) contain the term $L_x(n_1, n_2)$, which is not present in the formula (3.1). As a result, at equal values of all variables and parameters that are included in formulas (3.1) and (4.4), the values of these functions differ by $L_x(n_1, n_2)$. The so-called

entropy jump during the transition from a mixture to pure gas is due to the replacement of a function of the form (4.4) by a function of the form (3.1) and is inexplicable for those who believe that the sum of the entropies of ideal gases that form the mixture and the entropy of pure gas are functions of the same form.

Another formulation of the Gibbs paradox speaks of a paradoxical jump in the entropy of mixing when moving from mixing different to mixing identical gases (see, for example, [1,2,7,13,16,18–27]). This formulation is given at the beginning of the article. It is easy to show that, as in the previous formulation, the appearance of a conclusion about a paradoxical jump in the entropy of mixing is due to the replacement of a function of one form with a function of another form.

Suppose that the entropy of an ideal gas is expressed by formula (3.1), and the entropy of the mixture is the formula (5.1). Suppose also that the different mixable gases 1 and 2 have the same values of temperature and pressure, and in the limit of convergence of properties turn into the i -th gas. In this case, the entropy of mixing different gases ΔS_{md} is expressed by the formula (5.4), does not depend on the properties of the mixed gases and is equal to $L_x(n_1, n_2)$, and the entropy of mixing of identical gases ΔS_{mi} is expressed by the formula (5.6) and is equal to zero. Respectively, it can be concluded that the entropy of mixing different ideal gases remains constant as the properties approach each other, as long as the gases remain different, but vanishes abruptly when transitioning to identical gases.

Comparing formulas (5.4) and (5.6), we can notice that the fact that their values differ by the quantity $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ is due to the fact that the former formula involves the function of the form $S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T)$, whose formula (4.4) contains $L_x(n_1, n_2)$, and the latter formula involves the function of another form $S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)$, whose formula (3.1) does not contain $L_x(n_1, n_2)$. The so-called “abrupt change in mixing entropy” by the quantity $L_x(n_1, n_2)$ is caused by the replacement of a function of one form by a function of another form and is inexplicable for those who believe that formulas (4.4) and (3.1) express functions of one form.

Thus, all considered formulations of the Gibbs paradox arise from the fact that the entropy of an ideal gas, which is expressed by formulas of the form (3.1)—(3.4) and the sum of the entropies of ideal gases forming a mixture, are mistakenly considered functions of the same form.

Those who do not notice this error use a false premise in their reasoning: “the additive property of substances may be a non-additive function of the amount of substances” and then

try to explain the false conclusions obtained from the use of this premise. For example, such a property, additive in the case of ideal mixtures of various substances, may be non-additive in the case of a mixture of identical substances. Or like this: a function that is expressed by a well-known formula may have such behavioural features that do not follow from this formula. Unaware of the falsity of the premise, the use of which caused the appearance of false conclusions, some authors try to explain these conclusions without invoking the thesis of the falsity of the premise, others seek to eliminate them without eliminating the premise from which these conclusions follow. Since both are logically impossible, the search for an explanation or a way to eliminate the Gibbs paradox has continued unsuccessfully for many decades.

The same mistake explains the formulations of the Gibbs paradox, in which it is not the entropy that is discussed, but the free energy of ideal gases and their mixtures (see, e.g., [4,12]).

The free energy F is defined by the formula: $F = U - TS$, where U is the internal energy. Since the free energy of a mixture of ideal gases is found by summing the free energies of the mixture components, and the entropy of an ideal gas is determined from a formula of the form (3.1), the formula for the free energy of a mixture of ideal gases contains the term $TL_x(n_1, n_2)$. Since the functions of the different forms $T[S_1(n_1, V, T) + S_2(n_2, V, T)]$ and $T[S_i(n_1 + n_2, V, T)]$, which are distinguished by the term $TL_x(n_1, n_2)$, mistakenly are considered to be functions of the same form, different paradoxical conclusions arise, which are similar to those considered above.

6. Additional comments

1. The author has considered the formulations of the Gibbs paradox which emerge from the cases where the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases is defined by a sum of the entropies of the mixture components and the entropy of an ideal gas by formula of the forms (3.1)—(3.4), which contain terms of the form $Rn_i \ln(V_i / n_i)$. However, many authors see the essence of the Gibbs paradox in the appearance of a number of contradictions in the case when the entropy of an ideal gas is expressed by formulas containing the term $Rn_i \ln V_i$. These contradictions (and the corresponding formulations of the Gibbs paradox) are resolved by justifying the formulas containing the term $Rn_i \ln(V_i / n_i)$. In the framework of statistical thermodynamics, this is achieved by dividing the partition function by $N!$, that is, by moving to the statistics of indistinguishable particles (see, e.g., [5,10,11,14,16,17,20,25,27]).

Without going into the discussion of these formulations and their solutions, we note the following. The justification of the division of the partition function by $N!$ can be considered a solution of only some formulations of the Gibbs paradox. However, these solutions lead to formulations of the Gibbs paradox which are discussed above, and to several other formulations.

One of these other formulations is given in Ref. [29]. According to the Boltzmann formula $S = k \ln W$, where W denotes the weight of the state. In the calculation W , the partition function is divided by $N_1!N_2!$ if the mixture consists of N_1 and N_2 particles of different ideal gases 1 and 2, or by $N!(N = N_1 + N_2)$ if the mixture consists of N_1 and N_2 particles of identical ideal gases. Then it is discovered that the entropy of the system changes abruptly at $k \ln(N!/N_1!N_2!)$ with a continuous transition from a mixture of different to a mixture of identical gases by striving for the zero parameter of the difference of gases. The conclusion about the entropy jump here is due to the fact that the function, the formula of which contains $N_1!N_2!$, and the function, the formula of which contains $(N_1 + N_2)!$, are mistakenly considered to be functions of one form.

2. The well-known proofs of the Gibbs theorem, that is formulas (5.1), contain errors. In particular, many authors, for example, [1,13,22], were proving the Gibbs theorem taking as a basis the Dalton law. In this case, the following was overlooked.

For a binary mixture, the Dalton law (see, e.g., [2,6,13,15]) is expressed by the formula:

$$p_m = p_1 + p_2, \quad (6.1)$$

where p_m is the pressure of a mixture; p_1 , p_2 are the partial pressures of the components of the mixture.

Formula (5.1), which expresses the Gibbs theorem for a binary mixture, can follow from formula (6.1) only if the entropy S_i is a linear homogeneous function of p_i . According to (3.3), however, S_i is a logarithmic function of p_i . Therefore, the Gibbs theorem cannot be derived from the Dalton law. Other errors in the proofs of the Gibbs theorem, including those in the proof given by J.W. Gibbs, have been analysed by the author in Refs [39,40].

It should be added that stating that the proofs of the Gibbs theorem are erroneous, the author does not venture to state that formula (5.1) is false. He only states that formula (5.1) and any of formulas (3.1)—(3.4) cannot be true at the same time since from formula (5.1) and any of formulas (3.1)—(3.4) follows the false conclusion that the non-additive function of an additive quantity is an additive quantity.

3. Since the appearance of the Gibbs paradox is caused by a rather simple error, the question arises: why this error has not been identified for so long time?

In our view, the main cause of this is that all who tried to explain the Gibbs paradox regarded paradoxical conclusions as facts that are inexplicable in the framework of some theory, in particular, in the framework of classical thermodynamics. Therefore, they searched for the explanation of these “facts” within the framework of other theories and did not even try to search for and analyse the premises from which paradoxical conclusions follow.

7. Conclusions

The Gibbs paradox occurs from the fact that the entropy of a mixture of ideal gases is defined as the sum of functions (entropies of ideal gases) which are not additive in the case where ideal gases form a mixture. The entropy of the mixture determined in this way and the entropy of an ideal gas are functions of a different form. However, they are mistakenly considered as functions of the same form. This gives rise to different inexplicable (paradoxical) corollaries — different formulations of the Gibbs paradox.

The author called the article “Explanation of the Gibbs Paradox”, since it explains which error in the well-known discourse cause the most formulations of the Gibbs paradox. However, the article does not answer the question: how to eliminate this error and, accordingly, the Gibbs paradox? This question should be the subject of a separate study.

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